

ISic1532

I.Sicily inscription 1532

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of Vigna Cassia

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 13000

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἐνθάδε
2. κῆτε Κυρι
3. ακή δούλη
4. Βονιφατίας
5. ζήσασα ἔτη κ

Apparatus

text of Agnello 1953

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645031

Bibliography

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.38
undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 311 no.134

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